

Hetero-ring Formation from Anilino Derivatives of Succinosuccinic Ester.

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Libermann (*Annalen*, 1914, **404**, 272) condensed methyl succinosuccinate with ammonia, which yielded a coloured substance, dimethyl-2:5-diamino- Δ 1:4-cyclohexadiene-1:4-dicarboxylate. He also condensed various aromatic primary amines with succinosuccinic ester and obtained corresponding products, which on oxidation with iodine yielded corresponding terephthalates. The above work was subsequently supplemented by Migliacci and Gargiulo (*Gazzetta*, 1927, **57**, 914; 1928, **58**, 110).

The internal condensation of diarylamino condensation products of ethyl succinosuccinate (I) with formation of pyridine derivatives (II) has now been brought about by the action of alcoholic sodium ethoxide, and in many cases even by the action of concentrated aqueous sodium hydroxide solution; the resultant

pyridine derivatives can be represented by (II) or (III) on account of the possibility of keto-enol type of tautomerism which is borne out by experimental facts.

Compounds of this type are invariably coloured in the solid state (crimson, violet or blue) and dissolve to a yellow solution in caustic alkalis, the original compound being reprecipitated unchanged by

dilute acids. This remarkable change of colour on the addition of alkali is probably due to the keto-enol change. These compounds dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid yielding intensely coloured (blue or green) solutions from which the original compounds are re-precipitated on dilution with water. All the compounds described in this paper are intensely coloured substances ranging from pink or crimson to blue or green in shade. They dye wool or silk from an acid bath containing the dyestuff in fine suspension to beautiful shades; they do not however dye cotton. The absorption maxima of these compounds have been determined in the experimental.

The facts that the compounds dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid with deep blue or green colour and also that they do not liberate carbon dioxide on the addition of dilute sodium bicarbonate and do not yield metallic salts or esters, show clearly enough that they are entirely different from the diarylamino-terephthalic acids prepared by Libermann (*loc. cit.*).

The nomenclature of these compounds have been based on the consideration that they may be supposed to be derivatives of acridinolines (like acridinols of Clemo, Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1769) of the following skeleton :

The following aromatic primary amines have been condensed with ethyl succinosuccinate and the condensation products subsequently treated with alcoholic sodium ethoxide for internal condensation and formation of the corresponding hetero-ring compound: aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, *o*- and *p*-phenetidines, 1 : 3 : 4-xylylidine, α - and β -naphthylamines, *o*- and *p*-aminophenols, *o*-aminoacetanilide and *p*-aminoacetophenone. Attempts to prepare hetero-ring compounds from primary diamines and secondary amines were unsuccessful.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The condensation of ethyl succinosuccinate with primary aromatic amines were carried out with only slight modifications of the original method described by Libermann (*loc. cit.*) to suit individual

cases. The properties of these compounds, many of which have now been prepared for the first time, have been given in Table I.

The above mentioned anilino derivatives of succinosuccinic esters were then subjected to internal condensation to yield the final heteroring compounds. The preparation of one of them is given below. The rest were prepared in similar ways with slight modification according to individual cases.

6: 9-Dihydro-5: 22-dihydroxyacriquinoline.

2: 5-Dianilinocyclohexane-1: 4-dicarboxylate (3 g.) was refluxed for about three hours with a freshly prepared solution of sodium ethoxide (30 c.c. of 10 p.c.) in absolute alcohol. The colour of the solution gradually changed from dark orange to light yellow as the reaction proceeded to completion and the disodium salt of the condensation product was deposited in crystalline flakes at the bottom of the reaction vessel. The mixture was then cooled, diluted with water, filtered and the yellow filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a fine violet precipitate was thrown down. This was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol.

Generally speaking all these types of compounds are soluble in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid and pyridine etc., but insoluble in benzene or ether. The properties of these compounds are summarised in Table II.

TABLE I.

Condensation Products of Succinosuccinic Ester with Primary Aromatic Amines.

(-cycloHexane-1.4:-dicarboxylate=C).

Name.	M. p.	Appearance.
Diethyl-2:5-dianilino-C.	163°	Orange red needles.
Diethyl-2 :5-di-o-toluidino-C.	181°	Orange to deep rose red needles.
*Diethyl-2 :5-di-m-toluidino-C.	143°	Yellowish red needles.
Diethyl-2 :5-di-p-toluidino-C.	214°	Deep orange red needles.
Diethyl-2 :5-di-o-anisidino-C.	159°	Scarlet red prisms.
Diethyl-2 :5-di-p-anisidino-C.	191°	Orange needles.
Diethyl-2 :5-di-o-phenatidino-C.	201°	Scarlet red needles.
Diethyl-2 :5-di-p-phenatidino-C.	197°	Deep red crystals.
*Diethyl-2 :5-di-1 :3 :4-xyloidino-C.	155°	Orange red needlessly.
Diethyl-2:5-di- α -naphthylamino-C.	230°	" " "
Diethyl-2 :5-di- β -naphthylamino-C.	228°	Rose needles.
*Diethyl-2 :5-di-o-hydroxyamino-C.	122°	Deep red needles.
* " " " "	113°	Reddish brown crystals.
*Diethyl-2 :5-di-p-acetylaminoanilino-C.	179°	" " "
* " " " acetylanilino-C.	119°	" " "

* New compounds prepared by the authors.

TABLE II.

Hetero-ring Compounds.

(6:9-Dihydro-5:22-dihydroxyacriquinoline=Q).

Name.	Appearance.	Shade on wool and silk.	Wave-length of absorption maxima.	M. P.	Analysis Found.	(nitrogen). Calc.
1:17-Dimethyl-Q.	Violet prisms.	Deep pink.	4520	Above 280°	8.78	8.9 p.c.
2:18-Dimethyl-Q.	Bluish violet prisms.	Light red.	4870	Decomposed at 255°	8.42	8.18
3:19-Dimethyl-Q.	" needles	Pinkish violet.	4530	258°	7.7	8.18
1:17-Dimethoxy-Q.	Pinkish violet crystals.	" "	4530	212°	8.3	8.18
1:17-Dimethoxy-Q.	Violet needles.	" "	4370	260°	7.7	7.48
3:19-Dimethoxy-Q.	Deep violet crystals.	Bright red.	4960	" "	7.9	7.48
1:17-Diethoxy-Q.	Pinkish violet prisms.	Deep yellow.	4490	" "	6.6	6.96
3:19-Diethoxy-Q.	" "	Pink.	5170	218°	7.0	6.96
1:17:3:19-Tetramethyl-Q.	Deep violet needles.	" "	4460	Above 280°	7.4	7.57
1:2:17:18-Diphenylene-Q.	" crystals.	" "	4980	260°	6.98	6.76
3:4:19:20-Diphenylene-Q.	" prisms.	Light red.	5250	260°	7.12	6.76
1:17-Dihydroxy-Q.	Deep reddish brown crystals.	Brownish yellow.	4210	236°	7.6	8.08
3:19-Dihydroxy-Q.	Pinkish violet prisms.	Deep pink.	4710	205°	8.1	8.08
3:19-Diacetylaminoo-Q.	" brown crystals.	Yellowish red.	4990	212°	12.7	13.08
3:19-Diacetyl-Q.	Yellow needles.	Yellowish brown.	4530	158°	7.2	7.04

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